

Behaviour of Molybdenum Electrode in Buffer Solutions

M. M. B. EL-SABBAH, M. E. IBRAHIM, R. M. ABU-SHAHBA and A. A. ABDELLAH

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

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Molybdenum electrode upon immersion in buffered solutions develops a steady state potential that depends on whether the solution is air- or N_2 -saturated. Thus in one and the same buffer solution, the potential recorded in aerated solutions as a whole is less negative than that recorded in N_2 -saturated solutions. The effect of oxygen is therefore clear. The potentials in both cases vary linearly with the pH value of the solutions, at a rate of 45.5 and 51 mV/pH unit in aerated and N_2 -saturated solutions, respectively. The rates of oxide film thickening in aerated solutions of different pH values are computed from E vs $\log t$ (time) curves.

DUE to the complex corrosion behaviour of molybdenum, there is as yet no clear cut applicable picture. There is however, an ample information on passivation^{1,2}, polarization³⁻⁴ and potential^{5,7} of molybdenum. Chassing *et al.*¹ reported that the extent of the passivation region of the metal in HCl depends on the experimental conditions. Highly sensitive radioactive technique was used by Neiman *et al.*² to study the dissolution of Mo at a wide range of potentials including the passivity range. The authors concluded that passivity of Mo probably cannot be attributed to the formation of its oxides of definite composition, and the metal can be used as a corrosion resistant material. Johnson *et al.*³, on the other hand, reported that the passivity of Mo in H_2SO_4 containing K_2SO_4 solution is due to the coverage of the metal surface with Mo_3O_8 . The steady state potential of Mo electrode depends on pH of the electrolyte⁴⁻⁶. Shatalov and Marshakov⁵ demonstrated that Mo electrode vary its potential E , in chloride buffered solutions according to equation (1).

$$E = 0.375 - 0.045 \text{ pH} \quad (1)$$

Potential/pH diagrams were constructed by Pourbaix⁶, showing regions of passivity, immunity and corrosion. In the present work the dependence of the Mo electrode potential on pH of the solution was examined.

The results obtained were made use of in discussing the mechanism of oxide film growth in aerated buffered solutions.

Experimental

Open-circuit potentials of Mo electrode in ordinary aerated and nitrogen saturated buffer solutions were measured till constancy. Buffer solutions covering the pH range 1-14 were prepared¹⁰⁻¹² from AR chemicals, and their pH values were measured using calibrated digital pH meter with glass electrode.

Spectroscopically pure Mo rod (~4.23 mm dia.) were cut and welded to thick Cu wires for electrical connections. The resulting electrodes then fixed with neutral wax in Pyrex glass tubings in a manner that the weldings be isolated from the test solution. The area of the electrodes was ~2.5 cm². The electrode vessels had gas inlets and outlets and could accommodate a volume of 50 ml of the test solution. Before immersion in the solution the electrodes were abraded to the finest grade emery paper, degreased with acetone, washed with distilled water and dried between two filter papers. Five minutes before immersion of the metal and during the span of experiment stream of air (aerated) or nitrogen (deaerated) was passed through the solution. Each experiment was carried out with fresh solution and newly polished electrode, and repeated under the same conditions to ensure reproducibility, at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The variation of the potential of Mo electrode relative to SCE as a function of pH and immersion time in aerated and nitrogen-saturated solutions are represented by Figs. 1, 2, respectively. Inspection of these curves reveals that the immersion potential drift with time towards more positive values, reaching a steady state value after 20-60 min. This signifies further thickening of the pre-immersion oxide film¹³, which is in accordance with the high corrosion resistance of the metal³. In one and the same buffer solution the potentials recorded in the aerated solutions (Fig. 1) are as a whole less negative than those measured in nitrogen saturated solutions (Fig. 2), the effect of oxygen is, therefore, clear.

Steady state potential-pH curves in aerated and deaerated solutions are depicted in Fig. 3. It is quite clear from these curves that the Mo electrode potential varies linearly with the pH of the solution at a rate of 0.045 and 0.051 mV/pH

Fig. 1. Potential-time curves for molybdenum electrode in aerated buffer solution.

Fig. 2. Potential-time curves for molybdenum in deaerated buffer solutions.

according to equations (2) and (3) in aerated and deaerated solutions, respectively.

$$E_{Mo} = \text{const.} - 0.045 \text{ pH} \quad (2)$$

$$E_{Mo} = \text{const.} - 0.051 \text{ pH} \quad (3)$$

These results are in accordance with those previously reported^{9,14}. The variation of the steady-state potential of molybdenum with pH can be readily accounted for by considering that these potentials are mixed corrosion-potentials.

The shift of potential towards positive values (Figs. 1 and 2) indicates that the pre-immersion

Fig. 3. Potential-pH diagrams for Mo-electrode.

molybdenum oxide film found on the surface of the metal is not sufficient to impart passivity, and that healing and further thickening of the film continues till this state is attained. One can safely conclude, therefore, that the cathodic processes predominate over anodic ones. This can occur through either an increase in the self-polarization of the anodic areas or a decrease in the self-polarization of the cathodic ones.

In air-saturated solution reduction of oxygen, equation (4) represents the most significant cathodic process of corrosion.

This reaction occurs under the influence of an anodic current density i_a , which polarises the electrode and shifts its potential in the positive (noble) direction.

The mechanism of oxide film growth in relation to potential variations was treated by Abd El-Kader and Shams El-Din¹⁵. As is evident from the curves of Fig. 4, the potential of the Mo-electrode varies linearly with the logarithm of the immersion time. This behaviour can be readily understood when one takes into consideration the physical properties of MoO_3 covering the metal surface. This oxide is an n-type semiconductor¹⁶. Its conductivity is due to the non-stoichiometry resulting from the excess of the metal cations in the lattice.

Only under the influence of strong electric fields, of the order of magnitude of RT/nF per atom layer, can detectable ionic current flows. With these high field strengths Ohm's law does not apply, and ion transport is governed by the familiar Guntherschulze and Betz relationship¹⁷.

$$i_a = k_a \exp. (BH) \quad (5)$$

where, k_a and B are constants, and H is the effective field strength. The field is created from the adsorption of anions on the pre-immersion oxide

Fig. 4. E-log t plots for the Mo-electrode in aerated buffer solutions.

film covering the metal, which accelerates the migration of Mo ions towards the oxide layer.

Assuming, reasonably, that all potential differences in the electrical chain, other than the one across the oxide film, are constant and small, equation (5) can be written in the form

$$i_a = k_a \exp. \left(\frac{BE}{\delta} \right) \quad (6)$$

where, E is the electrode potential and δ is the thickness of the film.

Since, no Mo ions were detected in solution, one can safely conclude that the quantity of electricity, $Q = i_a t$, which passes per unit cm^2 , is used exclusively in increasing the thickness of the oxide. The increase in δ necessitates, however, a corresponding equivalent rise in the potential E, so as to keep the field strength E/δ the same. The logarithmic variation of the electrode potential is, therefore, a direct indication of a logarithmic growth law for oxide film.

If S denotes the density of the oxide, M its molecular weight and n the number of Faraday F, required for the formation of one mol of the oxide, it follows that

$$Q = i_a t = \frac{nFS \Delta\delta}{M} \quad (7)$$

and the increase in film thickness $\Delta\delta$, is

$$\Delta\delta = \frac{Mi_a t}{nFS} \quad (8)$$

The rate of oxide growth would thus be

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \frac{Mi_a}{nFS} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the value of i_a from equation (6) one obtains

$$dt = \frac{nFS}{Mk_a} \exp. \left(-\frac{BE}{\delta} \right) d\delta \quad (10)$$

Setting x for $1/\delta$, $d\delta = -x^{-2} dx$, equation (10) can be written in the form

$$t = -A \int \exp. (-BE x) (x^2 \cdot dx) \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{A}{BE x^2} \exp. (-BE x) - \frac{2}{BE} \int \frac{\exp. (-BE x)}{x^3} dx \quad (12)$$

where, $A = \frac{nFS}{Mk_a}$

The second term on the right hand side of equation (12) tends rapidly to zero, since x is very large (δ is small). Substituting for x by its original value $1/\delta$ in equation (12) one gets

$$t = A \frac{\delta^2}{BE} \exp. \left(-\frac{BE}{\delta} \right) \quad (13)$$

or

$$|E| = \text{const.} + 2.303 \frac{\bar{\delta}}{B} \log t \quad (14)$$

which describes the experimental results (Fig. 4).

$\bar{\delta}$ represents the rate of thickening of the oxide per unit decade of time. The constant B, is identified as¹⁸ :

$$B = \frac{nF}{RT} \alpha \bar{\delta} \quad (15)$$

where, α is a transference coefficient similar to that encountered in normal electrochemical reaction¹⁹, ($0 < \delta < 1$), and $\bar{\delta}$ is the width of the energy barrier surmounted by the ion during transfer. Assuming α to have an average value of 0.5, and $\bar{\delta}$ the value of 1.0 nm, B acquires the values of 39 nm/V. From the slopes of the E vs log t curves of Fig. 4 the values of $\bar{\delta}$, in solutions of different concentrations of the various pH values, have been calculated (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RATES OF THICKENING $\bar{\delta}$ (nm PER UNIT DECADE OF TIME) OF MOLYBDENUM OXIDES IN SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	Rates of thickening $\times 10^{-1}$
1.00	3.386
2.95	4.288
5.00	5.079
6.85	6.772
9.00	11.000
10.95	10.158
13.20	15.237

From a consideration of the data included in Fig. 4 and Table 1 the following conclusions may be drawn :

(i) The rate of oxide thickening in aerated buffer solutions (1-14) varies between 3.38×10^{-1} and 15.23×10^{-1} nm/unit decade of time, which indicates a decrease in the field strength with decrease of pH values of the buffer solutions.

(ii) The increased rate of oxide film thickening in alkaline solutions is expected, since the contribution of the reduction of oxygen in the cathodic reaction increases as the solution becomes more alkaline.

(iii) Straight lines obtained from E vs $\log t$ plot, (Fig. 4) indicate that equation (14) describes the behaviour of Mo electrode under the prevailing conditions. This supports the assumption that the oxide film thickening is induced by the field created at the metal-solution interface.

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